

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities JARH \(HEC-Recognized for 2023-2024\)](#)

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities JARH, 3\(4\) October-December 2023](#)

License: [Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International License for JARH](#)

Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo.org.pk/index.php/jarh/article/view/357>

ADVERSE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA BY HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY ON META SOCIAL NETWORK PLATFORMS

Corresponding & Author 1:	IRUM SINDHU , Lecturer, Department of Computer Science Sukkur, IBA University Sukkur, Pakistan, Email: irum.sindhu@iba-suk.edu.pk
Author 2:	FARYAL SHAMSI , Lecturer, Department of Computer Science Sukkur, IBA University Sukkur, Pakistan Email: faryal.shamsi@iba-suk.edu.pk

Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(JARH) Sindhu, I., & Shamsi, F. (2023). Adverse Use of Social Media by Higher Secondary School Students: A Case Study on Meta Social Network Platforms. *In Journal of Academic Research for Humanities*, 3(4), 205–216.

Subject Areas for JARH:

- 1 Humanities
- 2 Media Sciences

Timeline of the Paper at JARH:

Received on: 06-11-2023.
Reviews Completed on: 23-12-2023.
Accepted on: 24-12-2023.
Online on 25-12-2023.

License:

[Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International License](#)

Recognized for BWO-R:

Published by BWO Researches

INTL.:

Abstract

There is an escalating concern surrounding the extensive use of Meta Social Network Platform among adolescents in grades 9 to 12 has significantly evolved over the past 3 decades. It is evident from the past literature that extensive use of Meta Social Network Platforms among adolescents, has an impact on student's academic performance with signs of addiction. This research centers on higher secondary school students, studying in grades 9 to 12 in five esteemed high schools in the Sukkur district, of Sindh Province of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. This is quantitative research where a systematic sample of 275 adolescents participated, employing personally administered surveys for primary data collection. Key findings indicate a notable correlation between reduced Meta Social Network Platform usage and higher academic grades, signaling a negative impact on academic performance with increased platform engagement. This study not only contributes to the existing literature by addressing the academic performance- social media relationship among senior school students but also emphasizes the specific platform under investigation. Our discoveries emphasize how important it is to make people aware and put strategies in place to reduce the negative effects of using Meta Social Network Platforms too much on the school grades of older students. Future research aims to develop practical strategies, building on the hypothesis, to address the impact of social media on academic performance. This proactive approach is essential as these platforms continue to shape the lives of adolescents, necessitating measures for a balanced approach to technology use and sustained academic success.

Keywords: Platform, Academic, Strategies, Grades, Adolescents

Introduction

All areas of life have been affected by technology, but especially our kids. In recent years, extensive research has been conducted to examine the detrimental effects of technology on student's academic performance, with a predominant focus on either adult learners or young children. Surprisingly, there appears to be a noticeable void in the existing literature when it comes to investigating the impact of technology on teenagers, a pivotal age group ranging from 13 to 18 years. Addressing this critical gap in the research landscape, the present study undertakes a targeted examination of the influence of meta-platforms within social networks on the academic performance and scores of adolescents. By delving into this specific demographic, the research aims to shed light on the nuanced ways in which technology, particularly social media, may shape the scholastic achievements of teenagers, providing valuable insights for educators, parents, and policymakers alike. The upcoming generation of teenagers is divergent from their ancestors due to the advent of technology. With each passing day, their exposure to technology is increasing and causing various types of addictions. The contemporary young generation has a non-traditional connection with technology that is getting stronger and stronger as they are growing up (Beastall, 2006). As per the study (Veen & Vrakking, 2006), children of this generation naturally acquire the meta-cognitive skills required for various types of learning, such as learning based on one's inquiry skills, collaborative skills, discovery skills, learning based on one's networking capability, an active form of learning, learning through experiments, skills of regulating and organizing oneself, and the ability to solve problems without supervision or help. Moreover (Prensky,

2001) by portraying this generation as living creatures immersed in technology and surrounded by digital age toys like video games, cell phones, and video cameras, etc., it draws attention to their generational acquaintance and the degree of dependence they have on information and communication technology. Social networking websites, another technological milestone, have made it possible for millions of users to connect. Additionally, it has altered how individuals engage with one another. Due to social isolation, providing ubiquitous computing as social networking platforms is the direct source of addiction in both teenagers and adults (Pempek et al., 2009). Meta Social Network Platform is undoubtedly the most popular social networking service nowadays and was initially originally as Facebook.com by Mark Zuckerberg during the year of 2009 (Sindhu & Shamsi, 2023a). By the mid of next year, July 2010, more than five hundred million Meta Social Network Platform members had been found to use Meta Social Network Platform actively. Keeping in consideration its widespread usage among students, the Meta Social Network Platform launched its higher secondary school student update in September 2005. The number of users on the Meta Social Network Platform is growing every day; for example, in 2008, there were 100 million users, but on July 21, 2010, there were 500 million, and the growth rate in percentage was 153 percent in 2014. Adolescents are given consideration, just like people of all ages, because it offers them a variety of entertaining content. Similar to higher secondary school students adolescents utilize the internet frequently. higher secondary school students in Asia's top ten internet countries were given the seventh spot with 17.5 million online users, and it was discovered that social networking

platforms-using students make up half of all internet users (Nurudeen et al.,). Instead of using this valuable time to study, they waste it on these social networking sites, which has an impact on their academic achievement.

Research Hypothesis

In this paper, we use the term "non-user" for the students who either don't have an account or do not use the Meta Platform of social networks. To differentiate between a moderate Facebook User from an addict, we call "User" to the moderate user and "MetaFreak" to the students who extensively use Facebook and other Meta Platforms. Our research hypothesizes that A person who doesn't use the Meta Platform for social networking has a higher academic score as compared to the academic score of Users who are moderately active or MetaFreaks who are addicted to these platforms. In other words, the average (mean) score of NonUser, User, and MetaFreaks are not equal to 2. However, the null hypothesis is that there is no difference in the means of NonUser, User, and MetaFreaks 1.

$H_0: \mu_{NonUser} = \mu_{user} = \mu_{MetaFreak}$

(1) $H_a: \mu_{NonUser} \neq \mu_{user} \neq \mu_{MetaFreak}$

(2) H_a : Variable that is dependent
Attainment_{score}: Academic score of the Students
 Variable that is independent
Meta_{usage}: Meta social network platform Usage
 Frequency Target population: Students aged between 13 years to 19 years.

Literature Review

Increasing usage of the internet draws special attention to the analysis of its implications on senior school students because of its excessive and unrestricted use. Students are the foundations that strengthen social value and are regarded as the primary elements of social capital that a country possesses (Pasek et al.,

2009). The use of the internet for information is directly related to social capital indicators, although leisure time activities frequently hurt them (Shah et al., 2001). Without the slightest doubt, the use of technology can significantly increase the productivity of an individual. No one can deny it enhances social capital by increasing the competence of present-era educationists. Currently, over a hundred social networking websites are available connecting millions of users online. A survey (Liang et al., 2011) reports that the Meta social network platform has over five hundred million users. Social networks form virtual communities where users share their profiles (Sindhu & Shamsi, 2023b). Meta social network platform was developed in the year 2004. In a very short time, this platform has emerged as the most widely used Social Media Platform. This is now, the new favorite of billions of users around the globe. Every technical advancement has continued to be the focus of research and a source of discussion; this is also true of the development of social networking platforms (Faryal Shamsi, 2017). Several research studies have been examined in this regard to determine how social networking site users are influenced in both +ve and -ve aspects (Vondrackova & Smahel, 2012) reports that excessive use of social networking can result in enormous issues with education, psychology, health, and interpersonal relationships. Additionally, many academics continue to pay close attention to the effects of social networking platforms on the younger generation. Researchers (Cassidy, 2006) revealed that young students have started a new trend of rivalry based on how effectively they use social networking sites and how many friends they can add to their lists on the Meta social network platform. A research investigation states that

teenagers who are addicted to the internet have concentration and corresponding issues when they use social media, they find it troublesome to focus and their insignificant level of focus on academic content causes lesser academic scores (Ahmed & Qazi, 2011). According to research (Shamsi et al., 2019) billions of videos daily are uploaded on social network platforms. One of the types of Internet addiction that has been studied is social media addiction (Shamsi et al., 2023). The author makes significant points by outlining six key elements that characterize their conduct as addiction. comprehensibility, tolerance, quickswings in mood, deterioration, disinterest, and quarrels make up these six elements. (Griffiths, 2013). These six components are **Comprehensibility, Quick swings in Mood, Tolerance, Disinterest, Quarrel, and Deterioration**

Another study examines the more negative side of social networking sites. The author claimed that even though the purpose of using meta-social network platforms is to gather students online so they can collaborate, doing so leads to procrastination and distraction. As a result, class management systems should be preferred instead (Pychl, 2008). Social network addicts frequently believe they have a large number of friends, but in reality, all of their relations are considered to be virtual. This tendency to drift away from friends, family, teachers, and other interactions could be dangerous for both life and education. Students' mentalities are completely changed, leading them to harbor illusions. Students' virtual lives divert them from their studies and direct them toward pursuits that involve living in a fantasy world. As a result, the student gradually begins to hate everything academic. One of the common phenomena carried out by almost every social media

user is eavesdropping (Shamsi & Sindhu, 2021) where people try to understand others by spying on their profiles, likes, actions, comments, and other activities performed by them (Klovdahl et al., 1994). In research, Karpinski showed that multitasking with technology, particularly on social networking sites, has a negative influence on both productivity and efficiency in academic achievement (Karpinski & Duberstein, 2009). On the other hand, research conducted (Helou & Rahim, 2014) on higher secondary school students who attended various institutions stated unequivocally that their use of social networking sites had no negative effects on their grades. Additionally, (Stollak et al., 2011) demonstrate the inverse association (in terms of academic score) between the use of social networking sites and academic performance. Furthermore (Andersson, 2019) claimed that have zero correlation between social media usage and the academic score performance of students. Addiction to the Meta social network platform was linked to things like usage frequency, stress, anxiety, and difficulty falling asleep, according to Koc and Gulyagci. They were unable to discover any significant correlation with demographic characteristics, though. Numerous studies have revealed an association between the excessive usage of the Meta social network platform and the clinical indications of psychiatric diseases. (Koc & Gulyagci, 2013) (Rosen et al., 2013), Social media addiction jeopardizes the bonding and association individuals might have with one another and has a detrimental impact on interpersonal relationships (Tokunaga, 2011), and this phenomenon can significantly affect their self-esteem as well (Peter & Valkenburg, 2006). Enormous factors, social and psychological, can affect social media

addiction.

Guardian's attention is stated to have an important role according to researchers. Studies have shown that scarcity of family

affection (Huang & Leung, 2009) and fights between spouses and siblings (Yen et al., 2007) can cause dependent behaviors; Love and support from parents and time-to-time supervision (Lin et al., 2011) can decrease the in-favorable behaviors. The drive to develop a personal relationship, having too much spare time, and narcissistic conduct are just a few of the many variants that could contribute to social media addiction. Similar detrimental impacts on young people, particularly students, can occasionally be seen in how well they succeed academically. Surprisingly, still, no inference can be made for the relationship between the use of meta-social network platforms and academic performance after examining all of these studies. Additionally, university students are mostly adults and relatively mature. So they are aware of both the advantages and disadvantages of every situation. The target concern is the increased use of social networks by teenagers, it becomes the center of

attention. High school students are mostly immature and more drawn to social network platforms. Therefore, this study focuses on high school students of Sukkur, Sindh, Pakistan. The target population and sample are aged from 13 to 19 years. The goal of the study is to determine if the use of Meta social networking sites has an impact on the academic performance of the group.

Research Methodology

This research was conducted as a quantitative survey. The target population was adolescents studying in higher secondary section or O-Level Cambridge students studying in reputable schools of Sukkur city from the age group of 13 to 19 years. This population mostly covered the Academic scores from 9th to 12th. The flow of methodology followed in this research is illustrated in Fig. IV. First of all, the target population was sampled due to time and budgetary constraints. Furthermore, if we just consider Sukkur city; many high schools are providing higher secondary education. Therefore in the second stage, multistage-stratified sampling was performed, so that distinct categories of high schools could be selected. Then, a scaling tool (i.e. questionnaire) was developed to collect the primary data and peer-reviewed. A total of 400 revised questionnaires were distributed, among which 274 responses are considered in this study, the rest of the responses were excluded due to invalid data. The statements generated and finalized to be included in the questionnaire are as follows. Quantitative analysis of the collected data was performed through SPSS and the validation of results was performed through the Analysis of variance (One-Way-ANOVA) test. To analyze the correlation between student Academic scores (referred to as *Attainment_{score}*) and Meta social network

platforms usage frequency (referred to as $Meta_{usage}$) in the hypotheses expressed in the equation. (1) and (2). Descriptive statistics were used for demographic information of the sample. In the end, results were elucidated based on statistical figures produced during the analysis.

Sample Design and Data Collection

The correct number of adolescents studying in high schools in the whole city was unknown. Therefore sampling was inevitable. To carry out the research process effectively stratified sampling was achieved at multiple stages so that the picked-up sample could reflect the real target population. The size of the sample was estimated as 386-387 as recommended by (Wojbor, 2019) and the formula of the sample as per population size is indicated as equation no. (3).

$$N = \frac{(z^2)(p)(1-p)}{(e)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$S_1 = S_2 = n/2 = 200 \quad (4)$$

Stratified sampling was inevitable as the corresponding population was to be divided based on their school and the geographic region. The *first strata* S_1 represented the students of schools that don't allow open use of unfair means during exams and the academic scores are unbiased. These are the schools and colleges that operate under the Agha Khan University & Examination Board (AKUEB) and Cambridge International Examinations (CIE) (Hussain & Ali, 2010). Moreover *second strata* S_2 depicts higher secondary school students where academic policies and exam regulations are so lenient and flexible that academic scores can be tendentious (Kamboh et al., 2019). Equation number 4 was used to determine the total number of answers. The poll drew in 400 participants in all. The left-over responses were removed before the examination, leaving 275 valid responses that were returned.

Development of Scaling Tool:

In this research, the Likert scale was used to measure the academic performance of respondents. Because the Likert scale is cost-effective and does not require a panel of experts (Kothari, 2004). Furthermore, respondents are directly involved in finalizing and setting up the statements of the data collection tool. The 32 statements generated to finalize the scaling tool are shown in the section. A. The statements were ranked by a panel of respondents and 15 statements with the highest score were selected to be inserted in the final questionnaire serving as the research scale tool. Table I expresses the scaling/measurement tool as a questionnaire as a form used as a fundamental instrument to carry out the research.

1) Coding: This research required quantification of dependent and independent variables used in the hypothesis in equations (1) and (2). The variable $Attainment_{score}$ was directly observed in numeric form but $Meta_{usage}$ needed a scaling mechanism. Equation (5) illustrates the calculation of $Meta_{usage}$, where (n) is the number of statements in the questionnaire and w is the score of respondents concerning each statement.

TABLE I
Questionnaire Query Items and Feedback

Query Item	Feedback
Section 1	
Mention Age in Years	16
Mention Your Grade / Class	12
Mention Your Average Percentage in Exams	60

Section II

Do you have a Meta Social Network Platform account?	✓
Do you check Meta Social Network Platform frequently?	×
I am allowed to use Meta Social Network Platform anytime	✓
I use Meta Social Network Platform to make new friends	✓
I use Meta Social Network Platform for playing games? I manage Meta Social Network Platform Groups/Pages	✓
I chat with my friends using Meta Social Network Platform	✓
I use Meta Social Network Platform to check out others' updates? I use Meta Social Network Platform for time-pass	×
I frequently update my Meta Social Network Platform profile	×

Metausage=10 Attainment_{score} = 60

$$\text{Meta Social Network Platforms Usage} = \sum_{i=1} m^i \quad (5)$$

For the calculation of score m, each statement in the final questionnaire was weighted with a $m_i = 10$. The weights were ultimately used to aggregate the impact of frequent usage of (Metausage) on Attainmentscore. Finally, the respondents were requested to submit their responses on given statements just in 'affirmative' ($m = +1$) or 'negative' ($m = +0$).

Findings

Analysis of the age variable targeting higher secondary school students and O-level students revealed that almost 39.8% of the average age of the sample (n=109) was 15 years, with 21.9% (n=60) being 14 years old, 20.4% (n=56) being 16 years old, 9.9% (n=27) being 17 years old, 4.0% (n=11) being 13 years old, and 0.4% (n=1) being 19 years old, as indicated in the Fig. V. As a result, the sample's vast majority of participants were 15-year-old students. Also, on analysis of gender variable, there was found slight difference in the proportion, as 52.19% of the entire sample was comprised of male students and 47.81% were female as shown in Fig.V. An important parameter to be analyzed was the presence of Meta Social Network Platform account as shown in Fig.V, it was found that 67.9% (n=186) students responded that they have the Meta Social Network Platform account and the remaining 32.1% (n=88) replied that they don't possess a Meta Social Network Platform account.

Fig. 2. Frequency and %age Distribution: Independent (Age) Variable

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	13	11	4.0	4.0	4.0
	14	60	21.9	21.9	25.9
	15	109	39.8	39.8	65.7
	16	56	20.4	20.4	86.1
	17	27	9.9	9.9	96.0
	18	10	3.6	3.6	99.6
	19	1	.4	.4	100.0
	Total	274	100.0	100.0	

Fig. 3 Distribution of Independent Variable: Gender

So, analysis of these figures in our sample indicates that most of the adolescents are the users of Meta Social Network Platform. In this exploratory and descriptive study, the relationship between *Attainment_{score}* (in terms of percentage) and *Meta_{usage}* was examined. To explore this relationship, we applied Analysis of Variance (One-Way-ANOVA). Before conducting the One-Way-ANOVA all its six assumptions were properly checked.

- 1) In this paper, the dependent variable *Attainment_{score}* is taken as a percentage value which can be zero 0 at minimum and 100 at maximum.
- 2) The independent variable *Meta_{usage}* was divided into three groups Meta Social Network Platform i) nonuser, ii) Meta Social Network Platform user, and iii) Meta Social Network Platform MetaFreak based on frequency score achieved by respondent through equation.
- 3) Each Group means and the number of

instances present within each group is shown in Fig. V. As it can be seen that Meta Social Network Platform NonUsers have an average percentage value = 81.3, whereas the User and MetaFreak Meta Platform user's percentage values were found to be 77.026 and 75.9 respectively.

- 4) Since no response entry was repeated across the groups, the level of independence within observations was checked. Additionally, there were distinct response entries for each group.

Fig. 4. Meta Social Network Platform Account Holder V/S Non Meta Social Network Platform Account Holder

- 5) Three significant outliers were discovered during the examination of outliers and were eliminated using the Box plot technique. To prevent a detrimental effect on the one-way ANOVA result's validity, outliers were eliminated. The results before and after the removal of outliers are seen in Fig. V.
- 6) The normality test was used by Shapiro-Wilk to determine whether the independent variable had a normal distribution at a 95% level of significance. All three p- p-values were >0.05 (significance level), as seen in

Fig. V, demonstrating the regularly distributed nature of the data. ($p = .152 > 0.05$, $p = .172 > 0.05$, and $p = .217 > 0.05$). This supports the assumption that the data is normally distributed at a 95% level of significance.

- 7) To assess the assumption of homogeneity of variances in the analysis of variance (ANOVA) Levene's Test is used. The assumption of homogeneity of variances means that the variances (spread or variability) of the dependent variable are approximately equal across different groups being compared. According to Leven's Test results, we got p p-value of 0.180 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 ($p = 0.180 > 0.05$). This concludes that the presumption of homogeneous variance was satisfied, indicating that there is no difference in variance between the three groups.

Finally, after scoring all assumptions, One Way ANOV A ($\alpha = 0.05$) was performed on the dependent variable *Attainment_{score}* in the form of Percentage and independent variable *Meta_{usage}*. The One Way ANOV A main effect was statistically significant for these three groups ($p = 0.029$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 2$, $F = 3.595$) as shown in Fig.V which clearly shows that the difference among these means is not due to randomness but the difference is quiet significance. The p-value associated with the ANOV A is reported as 0.029. Because this p-value is less than the chosen significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), the results are considered statistically significant at the 5% level of significance.

Fig 5. Independent Variable Groups and Their Mean Values

Fig. 6. Box Plot Technique for Removing Outliers

This shows that there are meaningful and statistically significant differences in attainment scores across the different levels of *Meta*_{usage}. This is an important finding that contributes to the understanding of how *Meta*_{usage} impacts *Attainment*_{score} in this context.

Fig. 7. Shapiro Wilk Normality Test

		Tests of Normality					
		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
Percentage	User type	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
	Non-User	.099	78	.205	.945	78	.152
	Moderate User	.086	138	.203	.986	138	.172
	Frequent User	.084	88	.200	.973	88	.217

Fig. 8. One-Way-ANOVA Result

ANOVA					
Percentage	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	660.794	2	330.397	3.595	.028
Within Groups	24721.171	269	91.900		
Total	25381.965	271			

Fig. 9. Tukey Post Hoc Test

		Tukey HSD				
(I) User type	(J) User type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Non User	Moderate User	5.3826	1.6778	.003	1.339	9.245
	Frequent User	5.3967	2.8932	.025	.657	10.235
Moderate User	Non User	-5.3826	1.6778	.003	-9.245	-1.339
	Frequent User	-1.041	1.8531	.049	-4.262	4.471
Frequent User	Non User	-5.3967	2.8932	.025	-12.235	-.557
	Moderate User	-1.041	1.8531	.049	-4.471	2.383

To perform further analysis and to identify which specific groups differ from

each other we applied the Tukey Post Hoc Test as indicated in Fig.V. Between Meta Social Network Platform Non-User and Meta Social Network Platform MetaFreak: The mean difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.25 < 0.05$), suggesting a notable distinction between these groups. Between Meta Social Network Platform Non-User and Moderate Meta Social Network Platform User: The mean difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.005 < 0.05$), indicating a meaningful contrast between these groups. Between Moderate Meta Social Network Platform Users and Frequent Meta Social Network Platform Users: The mean difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.049 < 0.05$), suggesting a significant distinction between these groups. The results of the Tukey Post Hoc Test led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis likely stated that there is no impact of Meta Social Network Platform usage on the performance of higher secondary school students. The rejection implies that there is indeed an impact, and the differences observed are not due to random chance.

Conclusion

This scrutiny aimed to make inquiries about the significance and impact of social network Meta Platforms on the performance of higher secondary school students. A sample of about 275 students was taken by exploiting the ability to discern the school where academics and policy are enough that students are allowed to attempt exams in a free environment. The sample was further stratified into three strata concerning their usage of Meta Platform for Social Networking. These strata were meta-FB Nonuser, meta-FB User, and meta-FB MetaFreak respectively. As per the variation in the academic scores, the analyses revealed that Nonuser; User, and

MetaFreaks were significantly different from one another. The results show the insight that Meta Platform of social network is inversely proportional to academic score of higher secondary school students. Those students who do not use the Meta Social Network Platform utilize their proper time in their studies. However, those who use the Meta Social Network Platform are more drawn to the insights it contains, keeping them from giving their studies the time and attention they require. Most respondents of this survey were 15 years old or younger, different results may be obtained if students of various ages are included. By unveiling insights into the consequences of excessive social media use, this research enables the development of targeted interventions and educational strategies, empowering humanity to navigate digital platforms responsibly while maximizing their academic potential.

Recommendations

Future studies should prioritize investigating the comprehensive academic performance of adolescents who abstain from using the Meta Social Network Platform. As the digital landscape continues to shape the social and educational experiences of young individuals, understanding the potential impact of opting out of prominent social media platforms becomes crucial. Examining academic achievement beyond conventional metrics is essential, considering the multifaceted nature of contemporary education. Researchers should delve into aspects such as cognitive development, attention span, information processing, and interpersonal skills among adolescents who choose not to engage with the Meta Platform. This inquiry could shed light on whether abstaining from a major social media platform has discernible effects on academic success,

potentially offering insights into the complex interplay between online social interactions and cognitive abilities in the evolving educational landscape. Since the objective of this study was restricted to academic performance exclusively. However, additional factors, such as study time, exam planning, and extracurricular involvement, can be examined and contrasted. The explanation for these observations can then be investigated and further studied.

References

- Ahmed, I. & Qazi, T. F. (2011). A lookout for academic impacts of social networking sites (snss): A student-based perspective. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(12):5022–5031.
- Andersson, M. (2019). Examining Facebook use, self-compassion, and its interactions with subjective well-being.
- Beastall, L. (2006). Enchanting a disenchanted child: revolutionizing the means of education using information and communication technology and e-learning. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 27(1):97–110.
- Cassidy, J. (2006). Me media: How hanging out on the internet became big business. *The New Yorker*, 82(13):50.
- Faryal Shamsi, e. a. (2017). Reflections of practical implementation of the academic course analysis and design of algorithms taught in the universities of Pakistan. *Sukkur IBA Journal of Computing and Mathematical Sciences (JCMS)*, 2(1).
- Griffiths, M. D. (2013). Social networking addiction: Emerging themes and issues. *Journal of Addiction Research & Therapy*, 4(5).
- Helou, A. M. & Rahim, N. Z. A. (2014). The influence of social networking sites on students' academic performance in Malaysia. *International Journal of*

- Electronic Commerce Studies*, 5(2):247–254.
- Huang, H. & Leung, L. (2009). Instant messaging addiction among teenagers in China: Shyness, alienation, and academic performance decrement. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 12(6):675–679.
- Hussain, R. & Ali, S. (2010). Improving public school teachers in Pakistan: Challenges and opportunities. *Improving schools*, 13(1):70–80.
- Kamboh, U., Bukhari, S. M. A., Dehraj, M. A., Lakho, M., Ahmed, T., & Jamali, G. A. K. (2019). Analysis of the increasing trend of copy culture in the examination of higher secondary schools of Sindh.
- Karpinski, A. C. & Duberstein, A. (2009). A description of Facebook use and academic performance among undergraduate and graduate students. In Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, San Diego, CA, pages 5–10.
- Klov Dahl, A. S., Potterat, J. J., Woodhouse, D. E., Muth, J. B., Muth, S. Q., & Darrow, W. W. (1994). Social networks and infectious disease: The Colorado Springs study. *Social science & medicine*, 38(1):79–88.
- Koc, M. & Gulyagci, S. (2013). Facebook addiction among Turkish college students: The role of psychological health, demographic, and usage characteristics. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 16(4):279–284.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Liang, T.-P., Ho, Y.-T., Li, Y.-W., & Turban, E. (2011). What drives social commerce: The role of social support and relationship quality. *International journal of electronic commerce*, 16(2):69–90.
- Lin, M.-P., Ko, H.-C., & Wu, J. Y.-W. (2011). Prevalence and psychosocial risk factors associated with internet addiction in a nationally representative sample of college students in Taiwan. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 14(12):741–746.
- Nurudeen, Y., Ogbadu, E., & afaru Garba, S. J. Social network media and student academic performance in Kogi State University.
- Pasek, J., Hargittai, E., et al. (2009). Facebook and academic performance: Reconciling a media sensation with data. *First Monday*.
- Pempek, T. A., Yermolayeva, Y. A., and Calvert, S. L. (2009). College students' social networking experiences on Facebook. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 30(3):227–238.
- Peter, J. & Valkenburg, P. M. (2006). Adolescents' exposure to sexually explicit online material and recreational attitudes toward sex. *Journal of communication*, 56(4):639–660.
- Prensky, M. (2001). Digital natives, digital immigrants part 1. *On the horizon*.
- Pychl, T. (2008). Facebook whole new world of wasting time. *Psychology Today*, April, 3:2008.
- Shah, V., Kwak, N., Holbert, R. L., & Dhavan (2001). "connecting" and "disconnecting" with civic life: Patterns of internet use and the production of social capital. *Political communication*, 18(2):141–162.
- Shamsi, F., Daudpota, S. M., & Shaikh, S. (2019). Content-based automatic video genre identification. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 10(6).
- Shamsi, F. & Sindhu, I. (2021). Improving dblp efficiency through social media

- mining. *Journal of Information & Communication Technology (JICT)*, 15(1).
- Shamsi, F., Sindhu, I., & Fatima, S. (2023). Impact of computer gaming addiction on body mass index quantitative investigation about Sukkur city of Pakistan. In 2023 International Multi-disciplinary Conference in Emerging Research Trends (IMCERT), volume 1, pages 1–7. IEEE.
- Sindhu, I. & Shamsi, F. (2023a). Prediction of imdb movie score & movie success by using Facebook. In 2023 International Multi-disciplinary Conference in Emerging Research Trends (IMCERT), volume 1, pages 1–5. IEEE.
- Sindhu, I. & Shamsi, F. (2023b). Semantic social searching-an ontology-based approach. In 2023 International Multi-disciplinary Conference in Emerging Research Trends (IMCERT), volume 1, pages 1–4. IEEE.
- Stollak et al., 2011 Stollak, M. J., Vandenberg, A., Burklund, A., & Weiss, S. (2011). Getting social: The impact of social networking usage on grades among college students. In Proceedings from ASBBS annual conference, volume 18, pages 859–865.
- Tokunaga, R. S. (2011). Social networking site or social surveillance site? understanding the use of interpersonal electronic surveillance in romantic relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(2):705–713.
- Veen, W. & Vrakking, B. (2006). *Homo Zappiens: Growing up in a digital age*. A&C Black.
- Vondrackova, P. and Smahel, D. (2012). Internet addiction. In *Encyclopedia of cyber behavior*, pages 754–767. IGI Global.
- Wojbor, A. W. (2019). *First Course in Statistics for Signal Analysis*. Springer.
- Yen, J.-Y., Ko, C.-H., Yen, C.-F., Wu, H.-Y., and Yang, M.-J. (2007). The comorbid psychiatric symptoms of internet addiction: attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder (adhd), depression, social phobia, and hostility. *Journal of adolescent health*, 41(1):93–98.

APPENDIX

Statements to Scale Attitude on the Meta Social Network Platform

- 1) How often do you play games on the Meta Social Network Platform?
- 2) How often do you use/check your Meta Social Network Platform in a day?
- 3) How many hours do you spend on the Meta Social Network Platform?
- 4) I use the Meta Social Network Platform to only chat with my friends
- 5) Whenever I post something, I check my profile again and again to see likes and comments
- 6) Do you use the Meta Social Network Platform to stay in touch with family or friends you don't see often?
- 7) I don't like to play games on the Meta Social Network Platform
- 8) I consider the Meta Social Network Platform a waste of time
- 9) I consider the Meta Social Network Platform as a good leisure activity
- 10) How many hours do you spend on the Meta Social Network Platform
- 11) Do you upload photos regularly onto your Meta Social Network Platform?
- 12) I use the Meta Social Network Platform mostly in the late night hours
- 13) I mostly use the Meta Social Network Platform in class during lecture
- 14) In class, we mostly discuss Meta Social Network Platform posts and videos
- 15) How many Meta Social Network Platform accounts do you have?
- 16) Do you maintain any Meta Social Network Platform page?
- 17) I rarely check my Meta Social Network Platform account
- 18) I mostly discuss study material with my friends on the Meta Social Network Platform
- 19) I like to join Meta Social Network Platform groups that are related to
- 20) I update my Meta Social Network Platform status frequently
- 21) I enjoy meeting new people on the Meta Social Network Platform
- 22) I primarily utilize other methods to communicate with my friends.
- 23) I am only able to use the Meta Social Network Platform for a certain amount of time.
- 24) I'm not allowed to utilize the Meta Social Network Platform by my parents.
- 25) In my family, everybody has a Meta Social Network Platform account
- 26) My time passes quickly when I use the Meta Social Network Platform / play games on the Meta Social Network Platform
- 27) In exams, I spend less time / or don't use the Meta Social Network Platform
- 28) Meta Social Network Platform helps us to perform group discussions on assignments.
- 29) Do you believe that 'young teenagers' should have access to Meta Social Network Platform as easily as they do?
- 30) How often do you change your status on the Meta Social Network Platform?
- 31) Do you think you can improve your academic score if you have more available time to study?
- 32) Do you have school friends on your Meta Social Network Platform?